

Towards a standardized expression system of colors in fungal morphological description: color nomenclatural code for description works of specimens in Kun L. Yang's private herbarium (HTBM)

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Text

To standardize the color expressions in description works of specimens in Kun L. Yang' s private herbarium (abbr. HTBM = Herbarium of Turemugo Lab of Botany & Mycology), a color nomenclatural code is proposed here.

Article 1. All referred colors are limited to the sRGB (standard Red Green Blue) color space, including a total of 16,777,216 possible colors.

Article 2. One color one name in a single language, following the principle of priority, viz. for the name of one color in a specific language, only the earliest designated one is legitimate, and the nomenclatural starting-point is November 1, 2023.

Article 3. When referring to a color, both its color name and the hexadecimal RGB code should be included (e.g. licorice brown (#BFB075); 甘草褐色 (#BFB075)). A color name may contain three parts: an adjective (e.g. dark, light, pale; Table 1), an associative word (e.g. butter, tomato, withered), and a “color root”. The “color root” defined here is a general range of a series of hue (Figure 1), which is determined strictly according to the steps in Article 4. For simplicity, a color name may only contain an adjective and a color root, or only an associative word and a color root, but must not only a color root.

Article 4. A valid designation of a color should designate both its code and name.

4.1. Color Code Determination: 1) Positioning the target color from a high-quality photo with accurate color reproduction of the specimen by a computer color picker; 2) Improving the color positioning, eliminating chromatic aberrations caused by highlights and shadows with a visual judgment; 3) Recording the hexadecimal RGB code of the color (Figure 2).

4.2. Color Name Determination: 1) Converting the RGB code of the target color to a HSL (Hue, Saturation, Luminosity) code; 2) Checking Table 2 to determine the color root according to the value of Lightness, Saturation and Hue in the HSL code.

▲ Figure 1. Distribution map of the Color Roots.

▲ **Figure 2.** An example of Color Determination.

▼ **Table 1.** Suggested Chinese-English pair translation of common adjectives used in Color Names.

Chinese	English	Example		
		Chinese Name	English Name	Color Code
淡	pale	淡紫色	pale violet	#E4D3F8
浅	light	浅紫色	light violet	#CFB1F1
亮	bright	亮紫色	bright violet	#DC9FFF
中	medium	中紫色	medium violet	#E0BEF5
浓	strong	浓紫色	strong violet	#AC5EE2
深	dark	深紫色	dark violet	#8C27C1
污	dirty	污紫色	dirty violet	#C1B2D4
暗	dull	暗紫色	dull violet	#A38EC0
纯	pure	纯紫色	pure violet	#5500FF

▼ **Table 2.** Color Roots defined by Lightness, Saturation and Hue in HSL code.

Lightness (%)	Saturation (%)	Hue (°)	Color Root
[0, 5]	[0, 100]	[0, 360]	黑色 Black
(5, 95]	[0, 5]	[0, 360]	灰色 Gray
	(5, 50)	[0, 20]	红色 Red
		(20, 50]	褐色 Brown
		(50, 60]	黄色 Yellow

... continued below

▼ **Table 2.** (continued)

Lightness (%)	Saturation (%)	Hue (°)	Color Root
(5, 95]	(5, 50)	(60, 170]	绿色 Green
		(170, 240]	蓝色 Blue
		(240, 280]	紫色 Violet
		(280, 320]	紫红色 Purple
		(320, 345]	粉色 Pink
		(345, 360)	红色 Red
		[50, 100]	[0, 20]
		(20, 50]	橙色 Orange
		(50, 60]	黄色 Yellow
		(60, 170]	绿色 Green
		(170, 240]	蓝色 Blue
		(240, 280]	紫色 Violet
		(280, 320]	紫红色 Purple
		(320, 345]	粉色 Pink
	(345, 360)	红色 Red	
(95, 100]	[0, 100]	[0, 360)	白色 White

Additional notes:

This code is interpreted by the author and may keep updating in the future.

This code marks the color nomenclatural starting-point, and the first 22 colors with their name and code are designated in Table 3.

▼ **Table 3.** Colors designated in this article.

No.	Sample	Color Name		Color Code	Note
		Chinese	English		
1		甘草褐色	licorice brown	#BFB075	Designated here
2		铜橙色	copper orange	#A56B34	Designated here
3		深豆蔻红色	dark cardamon red	#6B392B	Designated here
4		猫鼬褐色	mongoose brown	#B5A284	Designated here
5		水蓝色	water blue	#D8E5F2	Designated here
6		黄铜褐色	brass brown	#B3794F	Designated here
7		驴褐色	donkey brown	#AC9B87	Designated here
8		灰烬褐色	ash brown	#C8BFB0	Designated here
9		淡紫色	pale violet	#E4D3F8	Designated here
10		浅紫色	light violet	#CFB1F1	Designated here
11		亮紫色	bright violet	#DC9FFF	Designated here

... continued below

▼ Table 3. (continued)

No.	Sample	Color Name		Color Code	Note
		Chinese	English		
12		中紫色	medium violet	#E0BEF5	Designated here
13		浓紫色	strong violet	#AC5EE2	Designated here
14		深紫色	dark violet	#8C27C1	Designated here
15		污紫色	dirty violet	#C1B2D4	Designated here
16		暗紫色	dull violet	#A38EC0	Designated here
17		纯紫色	pure violet	#5500FF	Designated here
18		乳白色	milky white	#F5F7FA	Designated based Yang (2023)*
19		沙橙色	sandy orange	#E6CF73	Designated based Yang (2023)*
20		土橙色	earthy orange	#CF8A45	Designated based Yang (2023)*
21		木乃伊红色	mummy red	#994D2E	Designated based Yang (2023)*
22		浅褐色	light brown	#B39966	Designated based Yang (2023)*

* Yang, K.L., Yang, Z.L., Zhang, M., Wang, G.S. & Liu, X. (2023). *Gautieria mianjin* (Gomphales, Basidiomycota), a new species of false truffle from China. *Phytotaxa* 594 (2): 119–129. <https://doi.org/10.11646/phytotaxa.594.2.3>

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